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**“THE ROLE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN
EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES”**

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Annotation: *This article discusses the use of information and communication technologies in preschool education, and its effectiveness.*

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The task of preschool education is the full and appropriate psychological, personal, cognitive development of the preschool child, the formation and development of leadership activities, the basic new formation of age. Therefore, it is not possible to mechanically transfer new information technologies to the educational environment of a preschool. The computer should become a part of the child's developmental environment, a factor in enriching it, intellectual development, creating a basis for the formation of new types of thinking. The advantage of using computer technology is the shift of the center of gravity from the methods of oral teaching to the methods of research and creative activity of educators and students. Consequently, the role of the educator in the educational process is also changing. He ceases to be a source of information, but becomes a partner, an assistant.

At present, the country is implementing a strategy for the development of the Information Society, which is related to the availability of information for all categories of citizens and the organization of access to this information. Therefore, the use of ICT (information and communication technologies) is one of the priorities of education. Modern society is developing on the basis of the use of new information and technical means, and there are more and more requirements for information in preschool education institutions. Information and computer technologies have been actively used in preschool education. The use of information and communication technologies in kindergarten is a pressing problem of modern preschool education. The importance and necessity of the introduction of such technologies in the educational process is noted in the "World Report on Communications and Information" prepared by UNESCO by international experts. In the

context of rapidly changing world, constantly improving and complicating technologies, information of education is becoming increasingly important. As noted in government documents, this direction of education development has been recognized as the most important national priority. For example, Chapter 2 of the "Concept of Modernization of Russian Education in the Period up to 2010", which focuses on the priorities of education policy, states: "Information to achieve a new quality of education. "Computer technology is now designed to be an integral part of an integrated learning process that significantly increases the quality, rather than the additional" weight "of education and training" ("Long-term from the concept of socio-economic development. "Federation for the period up to 2020"). Despite the adoption of the priority national project "Education" (direction of "Internetization of education") and the concept of the federal target program "Development of information in Russia in the period up to 2010", Russia still can not say that it is integrated. policy in the field of introduction of information technologies in the activity of preschool educational institutions. It is the introduction of AKT that will allow the full and successful implementation of the development of the abilities of the preschool child. Over the past 5 years, a number of events have been held in our country, which mark the rapid development of Internet technologies in preschool education:

Adoption of the information society development strategy at the state level;

- * Adoption of the concept of socio-economic development of the country until 2020;
- * Implementation of the "Electronic Russia" program;
- * Development of the national education concept "Our new school";
- * Connection of schools and kindergartens to the Internet within the framework of the national project;
- * Adoption of the Law "On Education";
- * The formation of social networks, etc. required a different understanding of the role of ICT in the educational process.

First of all, it is necessary to have a clear understanding of what information and communication technologies are and what specific work they need in a preschool.

The combination of information and communication technology is associated with two types of technology: information and communication. "Information Technology" "A set of methods, techniques and tools for storing, processing, transmitting and displaying data aimed at increasing labor efficiency and productivity." At the present stage, methods, techniques and tools are directly related to the computer (computer technology). Communication technology identifies ways, means, and means of human interaction with the external environment (the reverse process is also important). In these dialogues, the computer takes its place. It provides a convenient, individual, diverse, highly intelligent

interaction of communication objects. By combining information and communication technologies and their introduction into educational practice, it should be noted that the main task of their implementation is to adapt people to life in the information society. Information technology is not just computers and their software. AKT means the use of computers, the Internet, television, video, DVDs, CDs, multimedia, audiovisual equipment, that is, everything that creates a wide range of opportunities for communication. The teacher should be able not only to use computers and modern multimedia equipment, but also to create their own educational resources, which can be widely used in teaching activities. In order to successfully implement the educational program of the preschool in accordance with the requirements of the state, society, family, it is necessary to actively use information and communication technologies in each preschool. And for this, every teacher must be computer literate, qualified in the use of AKT in the process of teaching preschool children. Teachers who want to keep pace with NS Zamon need to explore the possibilities of introducing and introducing new AKT into their practical activities, to guide the child to the world of new technologies, to form the foundations of the information culture of personality. These tasks cannot be solved without updating and reconsidering all areas of work in the context of kindergarten information. Thus, in accordance with the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation No. 2151 of July 20, 2011 "FGT on the conditions of implementation of the basic general education program of preschool education", they set certain requirements for staffing. One of the main requirements is that the teacher has information and communication technologies and the ability to use them in the learning process. A teacher's communicative competence includes the ability to establish communication in a variety of formats: oral, written, discussion, visual, computer, electronic. The teacher should be able not only to use computers and modern multimedia equipment, but also to create their own educational resources, which can be widely used in teaching activities. Thus, the main task of our preschool now is to increase the computer literacy of teachers, to improve their skills in working with educational software packages, global computer network resources, so that in the future each of them can use a modern computer. technologies for preparing and conducting lessons with children at a qualitatively new level. Our MBDOU experience shows the real possibilities of realizing the main tasks of information in management activities, as familiar means of media devices for management: digital cameras, camcorders, printers, scanners, copiers, laminators, DVD players, televisions, mobile phones Internet access with the possibility. The share of teachers with AKT increased by 50% compared to the previous academic year, including teachers with zero computer experience. Therefore, in order to help and support teachers, on the basis of our

kindergarten, internship sites for teachers of preschool education institutions of the city have been created, which will increase the professional skills of teachers and information culture. Teachers' work experience and education are not important in the use of AKT at work, but the desire and aspiration to master AKT is important.

REFERENCES:

1. Qodirova F.R., Qodirova R.M. Theory of children's speech development and methodology. - Tashkent: "Istiqlol", 2006.
2. The state curriculum "First Step" is approved and published by the decision of the Board of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 7, 2018 No 4.
3. GI KHASANOVA “Programmed learning in the educational process
4. Advantages of using technology ”Jizzakh: 2020. 420 pages. 223- 225b